

EFFECT OF YOGA PRACTICE ON ACADEMIC MOTIVATION AMONG DISADVANTAGED COMMUNITY STUDENTS

Thupakula Linga Murthy

ICSSR Doctorate Fellow (Ph.D Research Scholar) Department of Education, Osmania University, Hyderabad, Telangana State-500 007, Email: lingamurthythupakula@gmail.com

Paper Received On: 21 JUNE 2023

Peer Reviewed On: 30 JUNE 2023

Published On: 01 JULY 2023

Abstract

Motivational orientation refers to the motivational attitude that the student adopts in learning inside the classroom, and thus the student integrates it into school activities for internal or external reasons. Students' motivational attitudes and beliefs about the learning process are related to cognitive engagement and classroom performance. Motivation is the activation of goal-oriented behaviour. Motivation is said to be intrinsic or extrinsic. The term is generally used for humans but, theoretically, it can also be used to describe the causes for animal behaviour as well. Various theories state that, motivation may be rooted in the basic need to minimize physical pain and maximize pleasure, or it may include specific needs such as eating and resting, or a desired object, hobby, goal, state of being, ideal, or it may be attributed to less-apparent reasons such as altruism, selfishness, morality, or avoiding mortality. This article studies the effect of yoga practice on academic motivation among experimental and control group of disadvantaged community students with reference to gender.

Keywords: *Academic Motivation, Goal, Disadvantaged Community.*

Scholarly Research Journal's is licensed Based on a work at www.srjis.com

Introduction

Motivation is a desire to accomplish a goal or a drive to carry out a specific behavior. Motivation described as a state that energises directs and sustains behaviour. Motivation involves goals and required activity. The word motivation is coined from the Latin word "movere", which means to move. Motivation is defined as an internal drive that activates

behaviour and gives it direction. The term motivation theory is concerned with the processes that describe why and how human behaviour is activated and directed.

It is regarded as one of the most important areas of study in the field of organizational behaviour. There are two different categories of motivation theories such as content theories, and process theories. Even though there are different motivation theories, none of them are universally accepted. Also known as need theory, the content theory of motivation mainly focuses on the internal factors that energize and direct human behaviour. Maslow's hierarchy of needs, Alderfer's ERG theory, Herzberg's motivator-hygiene theory (Herzberg's dual factors theory), and McClelland's learned needs or three-needs theory are some of the major content theories.

Intrinsic Motivation refers to motivation that is driven by an interest or enjoyment in the task itself, and exists within the individual rather than relying on any external pressure. Intrinsic motivation has been studied by social and educational psychologists since the early 1970s. Research has found that it is usually associated with high educational achievement and enjoyment by students. Explanations of intrinsic motivation have been given in the context of Fritz Heider's attribution theory, Bandura's work on self-efficacy, and Deci and Ryan's cognitive evaluation theory. Students are likely to be intrinsically motivated if they:

Extrinsic motivation comes from outside of the individual. Common extrinsic motivations are rewards like money and grades, coercion and threat of punishment. Competition is in general extrinsic because it encourages the performer to win and beat others, not to enjoy the intrinsic rewards of the activity. A crowd cheering on the individual and trophies are also extrinsic incentives.

Social psychological research has indicated that extrinsic rewards can lead to over justification and a subsequent reduction in intrinsic motivation. In one study demonstrating this effect, children who expected to be (and were) rewarded with a ribbon and a gold star for drawing pictures spent less time playing with the drawing materials in subsequent observations than children who were assigned to an unexpected reward condition and to children who received no extrinsic reward.

Goals provide direction for action, while action entails effort, persistence in order to sustain activity for long time. The effort levels working with difficult task and targets to gives some indication of motivation, working for longer period of time after encountering obstacles is also associated with higher motivation finally level of achievement is effected by choice effort and persistent, the higher the motivation and more achievement of task and targets.

Situational motivation is phenomena in which aspects of immediate environment enhance motivation to learn particularly things. Motivation determines the specific goal to word which learners strive. Motivation is also enhancing cognitive processing of an individual. Motivation actually efforts what and how information is processed because motivated students are more likes to pay attention and try to understand the material instead of simple going through superficially. Motivation determines what consequences are reinforcing and punishing.

One of the most important factors that lead one to their goals is the drive. This drive is known as motivation. It is a zest and determination with a kind of excitement that leads one to persevere to reach greater heights, in no matter what avenue of their life; be it personal or professional. The drive may come from an internal or external source. The individual determines this. The factors that motivate an individual keep changing as one climbs the ladder of age and maturity. And also, achievement of one goal sets the ball rolling for another one to be achieved. Thus, to be motivated is a constant need. There are times when one faces a period of de-motivation and everything seems bleak. It is then that they need to find what would motivate them back into action. For every individual there is a variable driving force. In fact, it is not just a single factor, but a combination of factors that lead people to achieve their goals. The fact is that with routine monotony steps in and then everything seems like stagnant waters. It feels like there is nothing new. Breaking this cycle of monotony has helped many bounces back with enthusiasm. This is why human resource managers create a training calendar, which will take away employees from the routine they are stuck to, as well as enhance their skills in various areas. Others pursue hobbies during the weekend, thus giving them something to look forward to, as each week comes to a close. There are people who redefine their goals and ambitions from time to time in order to fill them with newer levels of enthusiasm to achieve greater feats. One needs to take stalk every now and then and find the motivator required to carry them through.

Yoga education

Yoga education could help to equip oneself with basic knowledge about one's personality, to learn to handle oneself well in all life situations, to learn techniques of gaining good health, to develop a discriminative mind capable of knowing the real from the unreal and to face the dualities of life with equanimity. Yoga education can enhance all the activities of the students, be it academic or sport or social.

Yoga techniques provide improved attention in studies, better stamina and co-ordination for sports and a heightened awareness and balanced attitude for social activity. Yoga education can be integrated in school education during the time set aside for physical education teacher (P.E.T.) but in a calm and quiet place creating the proper atmosphere for its proper study and practice. Clear concepts are necessary in teaching Yoga. Yoga practices can be built around concepts like conditioning (preparation), synchronization, concentration, relaxation, self-reliance. A dedicated and dynamic teacher can create an atmosphere for learning. As Yoga deals with life and learning, these concepts should be integrated into life situations through various methods available.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the effect of yoga practice on academic motivation among experimental group of disadvantaged community students with reference to gender.
2. To study the effect of yoga practice on academic motivation among control group of disadvantaged community students with reference to gender.

Hypothesis of the Study

Hypothesis – 1: There is no significant effect of yoga practice on academic motivation among experimental group of disadvantaged community students with reference to gender.

Hypothesis – 2: There is no significant effect of yoga practice on academic motivation among control group of disadvantaged community students with reference to gender.

Sample & Selection of students: The sample for the study is selected through Random sampling method. One each school of boys and girls will be selected randomly from the available social welfare residential schools of Karimnagar district. This school will be identified based on random sample technique by the lottery method. From class 9th students boys 70 and girls 70 total of 140 students, as an experimental group 70 students as control group will be included the sample of the study.

Tool of the Study

The Academic Motivation Scale: A Measure of Intrinsic, Extrinsic, and motivation in Education. (1992) developed by Vallerand, R.J., Pelletier, L.G., Blais, M.R, Brière, N.M., Senécal, C. and Vallières, E.F. This scale assesses 7 types of constructs: intrinsic motivation towards knowledge, accomplishments, and stimulation, as well as external, introjected and identified regulations, and finally amotivation. It contains 28 items (4 items per subscale) assessed on a 7-point scale.

Analysis and Interpretation

Hypothesis – 1: There is no significant effect of yoga practice on academic motivation among experimental group of disadvantaged community students with reference to gender.

Table No 1: Experimental group: Academic motivation pre-test & post-test in relation to gender

Sl. No.	Gender	Test	N	Mean	SD	t-value	df	Sig.
1.	Boys	Pre test	35	3.90	0.40	2.402	34	
		Post test		5.02	0.20			
2.	Girls	Pre test	35	3.95	0.43	2.711	34	
		Post test		5.25	0.22			
3	Total	Pre test	70	3.92	0.41	2.557	69	0.05*
		Post test		5.13	0.21			

@ Not Significant

*Significant at 0.05 level

** Significant at 0.01 level

From the above table it can be observed that out of the total 70 students, 35 were boys and the other 35 were girls. The pre test mean score obtained for boys was 3.90 and for girls was 3.95. The post test mean score obtained for boys was 5.02 and for girls was 5.25. The t-value obtained for boys was 2.402 which was significant at 0.05 level of significance. The t-value obtained for girls was 2.711 which was significant at 0.05 level of significance. The pre test and post test mean score obtained for both boys and girls was 3.92 and 5.13. The t-value obtained for both boys and girls was 2.557 which was significant at 0.05 level of significance. It is clear from the table that distribution of scores of gender in the effect of yoga practice on academic motivation among experimental group of disadvantaged community students was found to be normal. Hence, the **hypothesis 1**, which states that there is no significant effect of yoga practice on academic motivation among experimental group of disadvantaged community students with reference to gender is **rejected** as there was a significant difference among boys and girls in academic motivation through the effect of yoga practice.

Therefore, based on the mean scores it was inferred that, in the experimental group of disadvantaged community students with reference to gender, girls were better than boys in academic motivation through the effect of yoga practice and it was statistically proved.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant effect of yoga practice on academic motivation among control group of disadvantaged community students with reference to gender.

Table No.2: Control group: Academic motivation pre-test & post-test in relation to gender

Sl. No.	Gender	Test	N	Mean	SD	t-value	df	Sig.
1.	Boys	Pre test	35	3.50	0.40	0.101	34	
		Post test		3.54	0.50			
2.	Girls	Pre test	35	3.61	0.42	0.103	34	
		Post test		3.63	0.53			
3	Total	Pre test	70	3.55	0.41	0.100	69	0.92
		Post test		3.58	0.51			

@ Not Significant

*Significant at 0.05 level

** Significant at 0.01 level

From the above table it can be observed that out of the total 70 students, 35 were boys and the other 35 were girls. The pre test mean score obtained for boys was 3.50 and for girls was 3.61. The post test mean score obtained for boys was 3.54 and for girls was 3.63. The t-value obtained for boys was 0.101 which was not significant. The t-value obtained for girls was 0.103 which was not significant. The pre test and post test mean score obtained for both boys and girls was 3.55 and 3.58. The t-value obtained for both boys and girls was 0.100 which was not significant.

It is clear from the table that distribution of scores of gender in the effect of yoga practice on academic motivation among control group of disadvantaged community students was found to be normal. Hence, the **hypothesis 2**, which states that there is no significant effect of yoga practice on academic motivation among control group of disadvantaged community students with reference to gender is **accepted** as there was no significant difference among boys and girls in academic motivation through the effect of yoga practice. Therefore, based on the mean scores it was observed that, in the control group of disadvantaged community students with reference to gender, there was no significant difference among boys and girls on academic motivation through the effect of yoga practice.

Findings

1. In the experimental group of disadvantaged community students with reference to gender, girls were better than boys in academic motivation through the effect of yoga practice and it was statistically proved.
2. In the control group of disadvantaged community students with reference to gender, there was no significant difference among boys and girls on academic motivation through the effect of yoga practice.

Conclusion

Academic motivation is important in increasing the student's attention and their time engagement into educational activities, focusing their attributions in success and failure to internal factors. This helps them in controlling the factors affecting the achievement of the learning mission, all of which contribute to increasing their effort, controlling their learning experiences, and increasing their motivation. Motivation determines the specific goal to which learners strive. Motivation is also enhancing cognitive processing of an individual. Motivation actually efforts what and how information is processed because motivated students are more likes to pay attention and try to understand the material instead of simple going through superficially. Motivation determines what consequences are reinforcing and punishing.

References

- Christopher, J. C., Christopher, S. E., Dunnagan, T., & Schure, M. (2006). *Teaching self-care through mindfulness practices: The application of yoga, meditation, and qigong to counselor training. Journal of Humanistic Psychology, 46(4), 494-509.*
- Fatiha, M., Sliman, B., Mustapha, B., & Yahia, M. (2014). *Attitudes and motivations in learning English as a foreign language. International Journal of Arts & Sciences, 7(3), 117-128.*
- Gilakjani, A. P., Lai-Mei, L., & Sabouri, N. B. (2012). *A study on the role of motivation in foreign language learning and teaching. International Journal of Modern Education and Computer Science, 4(7), 9.*
- Powell, L., Gilchrist, M., & Stapley, J. (2008). *A journey of self- discovery: an intervention involving massage, yoga and relaxation for children with emotional and behavioural difficulties attending primary schools. European Journal of Special Needs Education, 23(4), 403-412.*
- Vallerand, R.J., Pelletier, L.G., Blais, M.R, Brière, N.M., Senécal, C. and Vallières, E.F. (1992) *The Academic Motivation Scale: A Measure of Intrinsic, Extrinsic, and Amotivation in Education. Educational and Psychological Measurement, 52, 1003-1017.*
- Youssef, A. M. S. (2012). *Role of motivation and attitude in introduction and learning of English as a foreign language in Libyan high schools. International Journal of Linguistics, 4(2), 366-375.*